

Effect of Protective Coating of Rubber (*Hevea Brasiliensis* Muell Arg.) Tapping Panel on the Regeneration of the Tapped Bark

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Abstract

The tapping panel, rubber extraction area of the rubber tree, is very valuable in rubber cultivation. Indeed, the fast and efficient regeneration of the bark is a major concern. Thus, a study to test a protective coating of the tapping panel to ensure a better and faster regeneration of its bark was investigated on GT 1 clone in South-Eastern Côte d'Ivoire. It was conducted in a "one tree plot design" statistical system with 120 trees equitably divided into four treatments. The rubber trees were subjected to downward tapping for the first four years after opening the tapping panel. Application of the protective coating alone affected negatively iso-diametric growth of the trunk and regeneration of the tree panel bark. Likewise, it has exacerbated the susceptibility to rubber tree tapping panel dryness syndrome. In contrast, the addition of ANA methyl ester to this coating favorably influenced iso-diametric growth of the trunk, regeneration of bark of the tapping panel, and reduced susceptibility to tapping panel dryness syndrome. The addition of ANA methyl ester at 5% to the protective coating of the rubber tree tapping panel gives it a certain efficiency, especially for the regeneration of its bark.

Keywords: Protective plaster, rubber production, radial vegetative growth, physiological parameters, tapping panel dryness sensitivity, Côte d'Ivoire

1. INTRODUCTION

Hevea brasiliensis, the world's leading source of natural rubber (Rajagopal *et al.*, 2003, Sekhar, 1989) is mainly grown for its latex. It is obtained by tapping. Tapping is the process of making a notch or incision in the bark, to expell the contents of the severed laticiferous vessels, the latex (Obouayeba, 2005; Obouayeba *et al.*, 2000; Thomas *et al.*, 1995; Auzac and Jacob, 1989; Gomez, 1982). The latex gives the natural rubber that is prized for its various qualities of plasticity and elasticity (Compagnon, 1986; De Padirac, 1986). Natural rubber is used in various fields, particularly in the tire industry (Compagnon, 1986). Studies on genetic selection of clones for latex harvest have contributed to the improvement and sustainability of rubber productivity have led to a substantial increase in the yield of trees (Tonnelier, 1981, Obouayeba, 2005, Eschbach *et al.*, 1984, Prévot *et al.*, 1986, Lacrotte, 1991); and consequently of plantations (Eschbach and Tonnelier, 1984, Obouayeba, 2005).

Despite these high yields, in Côte d'Ivoire (having one of the best yields in the world- 1650 kg. ha⁻¹), concerns remain in the modernization and the sustainability of the production management practices. The concern is the stabilization of this plant in cultivated areas, favorable and/or marginal, with good yields throughout the latex harvesting period of 30 to 35 years (Obouayeba *et al.*, 2008), to considerably reduce the use of forest lands.

The lack of mastery of tapping techniques, particularly the overconsumption of bark, is a major concern. Majority of tappers excessively consume the bark of the downward panel so that it is finished in 5 or 6 years instead of the expected 12 to 14 years (Gohet *et al.*, 1991). Such practices significantly reduce the latex harvest time from 30 to 35 years, to be between 20 to 30 years (Obouayeba *et al.*, 2008). Tapping on the regenerated bark, the downward tapping panel (BI) planned for commencement at least 10 years after opening, takes place within 6 to 7 years. It is known that a bark can be tapped at least three times (Obouayeba, 2003, personal communication). If bark regeneration is good, following a tapping (which preserves the cambium). The thickness of the regenerated bark, with or without the use of some chemicals, and the time taken to reconstitute it are important factors. Obouayeba *et al.* (2002) and Obouayeba (2005), have shown that mature tapping bark is 6 mm thick. The effect of a protective coating on the bark renewal was studied on *Hevea brasiliensis* clone GT1 for four years on the experimental and production station of CNRA-Anguédedou, in the south-east of Côte d'Ivoire.

2 - MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 - Plant material

The plant material used is of clone GT 1. It has moderate vegetative growth (Obouayeba *et al.*, 2000) and metabolic activity (Jacob *et al.*, 1988). The tree yield is not very high but, largely compensated by its steady performance (Anonymous, 1993). It is the most popular clone in Côte d'Ivoire because of its hardiness and resistance to tapping panel dryness (Chapuset, 2001). It has physiological and biochemical characteristics favorable to production (Anonymous, 1993). Its resistance to tapping panel dryness and wind breakage (Chapuset *et al.*, 2000) makes it a popular clone especially in small holdings.

2.2 - Methods

2.2.1 - Experimental set up and selection of trees

The lay out of the trial is of a "one tree plot design", that is to say, one tree constitutes a replication. A total of 120 trees were selected based on circumference and the health status. This selection was made avoiding the border trees and those trees adjacent to trees attacked by root rot caused by *Fomes lignosus*. The average trunk circumference of the selected trees at 1 meter above the ground was 50 cm. These trees were divided into four distinct treatments, with 30 trees (replicates) per treatment. This trial was set up at the CNRA-Anguédedou experimentation and production station in south-eastern Côte d'Ivoire.

2.2.2 - Treatments

The trees were opened at 1.20 m from the ground (BO-1). The different treatments applied to the trees are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Different treatments applied to trees

N° Order	Treatments	Designation
1	S/2 d3 6d/7 0/y	Tapping half-spiral downward every three days, six working days out of seven; without hormonal stimulation.
2	S/2 d3 6d/7 ET2.5% Pa1(1) 6/y	Tapping half-spiral downward every three days, six working days out of seven; stimulation with 2.5% concentrated Ethephon with application on a tapping panel at the rate of 1 g of stimulant on a band 1 cm wide; 6 stimulations are performed per year.
3	S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating	Tapping half-spiral downward, every three days, six working days out of seven; associated with protective coating alone, without hormonal stimulation.
4	S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating ANA 5%	Tapping half-spiral downward every three days, six working days out of seven; combined with protective coating, with stimulation using 5% concentrated ANA methyl ester

2.2.2.1 - Tapping

For all four treatments, the type of tapping adopted is the downward half-spiral tapping performed every three days, six working days out of seven; Sunday being a day of repose. This tapping is alternated annually on panels A (BO-1) and B (BO-2) from the third year of exploitation.

2.2.2.2 - Stimulation

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The stimulating product, whatever its nature, was applied on the tapping panel of the selected trees, on a strip of 1 cm in width, equivalent to 1 g of stimulating product per tree. The stimulating paste having active substance Ethephon at a concentration of 2.5% was obtained by mixing Ethrel and palm oil. That having as active ingredient the 5% concentrated ANA methyl ester was obtained by mixing aqueous coating and ANA methyl ester. This coating is a vinylic paint with water leaving a protective film on the treated surface.

2.2.3 - Measured parameters

For each parameter, the annual average of the measurements carried out was recorded.

2.2.3.1 – Production

The rubber production of each treatment was weighed every 4 weeks using a scale. Fresh rubber samples were taken for each treatment to determine the dry rubber production (drc) and yield per tree was calculated ($\text{g.t}^{-1}.\text{t}^{-1}$).

2.2.3.2 - Isodiametric growth (girth increment) and bark depth

Trunk circumferences and tree bark depths were measured annually in July (opening of trees in July 1984). The circumference measurements were made at the height of 1.70 m from the ground using a measuring tape. Those relating to bark depth were made using a brush and a ruler on the regenerating bark on the tapping panel in the first year of the experiment.

2.2.3.3 - Visual estimate of tapping panel dryness

The visual estimation method is used to account for the onset and progress of the tapping panel dryness (Van De Sype, 1984). For each tapped tree, a number between 0 and 6 has been assigned and the meaning of which is as follows:

- 0, for a healthy tapping panel dryness,
- 1, for a tapping panel dryness on 1 to 20% of its length (10% on average),
- 2, for a tapping panel dryness on 21 to 40% of its length (30% on average),
- 3, for a tapping panel dryness on 41 to 60% of its length (50% on average),
- 4, for a tapping panel dryness on 61 to 80% of its length (70% on average),
- 5, for a tapping panel dryness on 81 to 99% of its length (90% on average),
- 6, for total tapping panel dryness.

For each plot, the accurate count of the condition of the trees was recorded and the percentage of total cut length (LEM%) for each treatment was calculated as follows:

$$\text{LEM (\%)} = (0,1 n_1 + 0,3 n_2 + 0,5 n_3 + 0,7 n_4 + 0,9 n_5 + n_6 + \text{ES}) \times N^{-1}$$

N: Total number of trees; ni: Number of trees per dry cut length class; ES: Number of trees with bleeding already stopped for total dry cut.

2.2.3.4 - Latex micro diagnosis

From the latex collected, the levels of solids content (Ex.S), sucrose (Sac), inorganic phosphorus (Pi) and thiol groups (R-SH) were determined annually using the Latex Micro Diagnostic (MDL) method. The determination of the solids content was made according to the method described by Eschbach *et al.* (1984), while sucrose, inorganic phosphorus and thiol groups were obtained, respectively according to Ashwel (1957), Taussky and Shorr (1953) and Boyne and Ellman (1972). The MDL data were analyzed based on the reference values established by Jacob *et al.* (1987) and interpreted according to the interpretation scheme of Roussel (Jacob *et al.*, 1987).

2.3- Statistical analysis

Rubber production data, latex micro-diagnostic data, iso-diametric tree trunk growth and physiological indices were analyzed using the XLSTAT-Pro 7.5 statistical software. The Student-Newman-Keuls test and the Scheffe test were used to distinguish groups at the 5% threshold.

For percentage values of dry cut length, the Kruskal Wallis 5% test was used to determine significant differences.

3. RESULTS

3.1- Agronomic parameters

The different treatments applied to trees significantly influenced the agronomic parameters of these trees (Table 2)

In rubber production, treatment 3 (S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating) was the most productive ($36.9 \text{ g.t}^{-1}\text{t}^{-1}$). However, this yield and those generated by treatments 2 (S/2 d3 6d/7 ET2.5% Pa1(1) 6/y: $36.5 \text{ g.t}^{-1}\text{t}^{-1}$) and 4 (S/2 d3 6d/7 5% ANA Coating: $34.2 \text{ g.t}^{-1}\text{t}^{-1}$) were statistically equivalent. Treatment without stimulation or protective coating showed the lowest yield ($25.3 \text{ g.t}^{-1}\text{t}^{-1}$).

With respect to radial vegetative growth, the treatment with protective coating without hormonal stimulation expressed the lowest iso-diametric growth of tree trunks ($1.9 \text{ cm. year}^{-1}$). The isodiametric increase in the trunk of the trees was statistically identical for the other treatments, although the one without hormonal stimulation or protective coating showed a higher value (2.9 mm).

As for the thickness of the bark of the treated trees, the treatment without stimulation or protective coating recorded the highest value (8.4 mm), which was statistically identical to that displayed by the treatment with protective coating and stimulated with ANA methyl ester concentrated to 5% (7.6 mm). Conversely, treatment with simple protective coating showed the lowest bark thickness (5.6 mm) and the stimulated treatment with Ethephon (6.8 mm).

Table 2. Average annual values of agronomic parameters presented by rubber trees subjected to different treatments for four years

Treatments	Production ($\text{g.t}^{-1}\text{t}^{-1}$)	Tree trunk growth (cm.year^{-1})	Thickness of bark (mm)
1. S/2 d3 6d/7 0/y	25.3b	2.9a	8.4 a
2. S/2 d3 6d/7 ET2.5% Pa1(1) 6/y	36.5a	2.3a	6.8 b
3. S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating	36.9a	1.9b	5.6 c
4. S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating ANA 5%	34.2a	2.6a	7.6 ab

The average values assigned to the same letter are not significantly different (Newman-Keuls test at 5%).

3.2- Sensitivity to tapping panel dryness

The susceptibility to tapping panel dryness syndrome of treated trees was significantly influenced by the different treatments applied to the trees (Table 3). It varied from 0.1 to 1.3%. The single-plaster treatment recorded the highest tapping panel dryness rate (1.3%). This rate was followed, in descending order, by that of Ethephon treatment (0.6%) and that without hormonal stimulation or protective coating (0.2%). Protective coating treatment stimulated with 5% concentrated ANA methyl ester showed the lowest tapping panel dryness rate (0.1%).

With regard to the death of trees, no trees were lost due to the treatments applied

Table 3. Average annual tapping panel dryness and death of tree presented by rubber trees subjected to different treatments for four years

Treatments	Tapping panel dryness rates (%)	Death of tree rates (%)
S/2 d3 6d7 0/y	0.1d	0
S/2 d3 6d7 Pa1(1) ET2.5% 6/y	0.6b	0
S/2 d3 6d7 Coating	1.3a	0
S/2 d3 6d7 Coating ANA 5%	0.2c	0

The average values assigned to the same letter are not significantly different (Newman-Keuls test at 5%).

3.3- Physiological Parameters and Profile

The different treatments applied to the trees did not have a major influence on the solids content (ExS) of the latex (Table 4). The other physiological parameters have undergone a treatment effect. For sugar (Suc), the highest content was observed for the single coating treatment (12.8 mmol.l^{-1}), which was statistically identical to that expressed by treatment without hormonal stimulation or protective coating (12.0 mmol.l^{-1}).

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These two levels were very high relative to those of a clone with moderate metabolism (contents ≥ 12 mmol.l⁻¹, reference value). The sucrose content expressed by the Ethephon treatment, although was the lowest, it was statistically similar to that displayed by the coated treatment and stimulated with ANA methyl ester. These two levels were high (12 mmol.l⁻¹ > contents ≥ 9 mmol.l⁻¹, reference value). For the level of inorganic phosphorus (Pi) and thiol groups (R-SH), the Ethephon treatment was distinguished from the others by its highest values (Pi: 7.8 mmol.l⁻¹; R-SH: 0.8 mmol.l⁻¹). The content was very low for inorganic phosphorus (<10 mmol.l⁻¹, reference value) and high for thiol compounds (0.8 mmol.l⁻¹, reference value). The other treatments showed statistically equivalent levels, both in terms of inorganic phosphorus and of thiol groups. They were also very low for inorganic phosphorus (<10 mmol.l⁻¹, reference value) and medium for thiol groups (6 mmol.l⁻¹ > contents ≥ 8 mmol.l⁻¹; reference).

Analysis of the physiological parameters showed that the physiological profile of the treatment with simple protective coating, the treatment with protective coating stimulated with ANA 5% and that of the treatment without hormonal stimulation or protective coating were fairly balanced, while that of Ethephon-stimulated treatment is well balanced.

Table 4. Mean annual values of physiological parameters presented by rubber trees subjected to different treatments for four years

Treatments	Ex.S (%)	Sacc (mmol.l ⁻¹)	Pi (mmol.l ⁻¹)	RS-H (mmol.l ⁻¹)	Physiological Profile
S/2 d3 6d/7 0/y	39.4a	12.0a	4.1b	0.6b	Enough well balanced
S/2 d3 6d/7 ET2.5% Pa1(1) 6/y	38.4a	9.1b	7.8a	0.8a	Well balanced
S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating	40.2a	12.8a	4.5b	0.7b	Enough well balanced
S/2 d3 6d/7 Coating ANA 5%	39.7a	9.6b	4.9b	0.7b	Enough well balanced

The average values assigned to the same letter are not significantly different (Newman-Keuls test at 5%).

DISCUSSION

The latex harvesting system without stimulation or protective coating is distinguished by its lower rubber production. This level of production demonstrates that exogenous stimulation associated with tapping adequately improves the productivity of rubber trees (Traoré *et al.*, 2014). By analogy, the statistical equivalence of rubber production at the level of other treatments could mean that the protective coating, which is vinylic in nature with water, has a stimulating effect on the rubber production. Stimulation, by activating the production function of the rubber trees, causes an increase in the energy and assimilate requirements (minerals, enzymes and organic elements) necessary for the synthesis of the constituents of the latex, and therefore of the rubber production (Gohet, 1996; Lacote *et al.*, 2010). Faced with these increased needs, the laticiferous cells (Jacob *et al.*, 1995a) use the reserves in case of shortage of assimilates (Jacob *et al.*, 1988). The immediate consequence of this action is the reduction of vegetative growth (Obouayeba *et al.*, 2000; Obouayeba, 2005). This probably accounts for the smallest iso-diametric trunk and bark thickness growth of trees with only plaster treatment that resulted in the highest rubber production, although this production was statistically equivalent to that of most other treatments.

The treatment with the plaster alone has a greater negative impact on vegetative growth and bark thickness compared to other treatments. This would be due to the inhibitory effect of acetate-induced cell growth highlighted by Anonymous (2018a) and by Pinhal's (2015) work on *Escherichia coli*. Indeed, acetate is part of the components of vinyl paint (Anonymous, 2018b) which served as a protective coating. However, the addition of naphthalene acetic acid (ANA) to the protective coating of a water based vinyl paint results in less rubber production than other treatments and an increase in the iso-diametric growth of the trees trunk and the thickness of the bark. This reflects an antagonism vis-à-vis the combination of naphthalene acetic acid (ANA) to the protective coating of vinyl paint. This antagonism had no significant effect on the rubber production of the tree. This is not the case for vegetative growth and the thickness of the bark. ANA thus attenuates the inhibitory effect of vinyl paint. This is because ANA is an auxin, a phyto-hormone for growth of vegetative cells.

Regarding sensitivity to tapping panel dryness syndrome, the average tapping panel dryness rate of trees over four years, regardless of treatment, was very low. The low tapping panel dryness rates are indicative of a very good level of resistance to tapping panel dryness syndrome (Jacob *et al.*, 1987). The absence of dead trees recorded, whatever the treatment, also confirms this. The coating alone treatment gave the highest

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rubber production, statistically identical to that of other treatments, (except that of treatment without stimulation or protective coating) but expressed the highest rate of tapping panel dryness. This result shows that the application of vinyl paint on the rubber tapping panel has a negative effect on the trees sensitivity to the tapping panel dryness, compared to other treatments. This may be due to the inhibitory effect of vinyl paint on cell growth as previously mentioned. The inhibition weakens the laticiferous system, leads to physiological fatigue and to the tapping panel dryness. This highlights the detrimental effect of the use of vinyl paint as a tapping-panel protective coating. The results for iso-diametric growth and bark thickness expressed by this practice, in this study, confirm this observation. The analysis of the physiological parameters of the latex over four years of experimentation reveals that the rate of dry rubber content of the latex is high, regardless of the treatment. This is a reflection of a good regeneration of the latex exported during the tapping because the latex dry matter content, reflect the efficiency of isoprene syntheses in the laticiferous cells (**Jacob et al., 1998**). For **Gohet et al. (1996)**, this good regeneration of latex exported during tapping is an indicator of good rubber production. In terms of sucrose, the average levels expressed by the system without stimulation or protective coating and the one with protective coating alone are of a very high level while those of other treatments are of a high level, compared to the reference values established by **Jacob et al (1987)**. These results indicate a good to very good supply of photosynthates for the treated trees (**Gohet, 1996**). The good to very high levels of sucrose content are due to the fact that the inorganic phosphorus levels, regardless of the treatment, is very low, compared to the reference values established by **Jacob et al (1987)**. This does not sufficiently activate the metabolism of rubber production (**Gohet, 1996**). The inorganic phosphorus contained in the latex can be considered as an indicator of the energy intensity of the metabolism of the laticiferous cells (**Jacob et al., 1988**). Exogenous energy provided by stimulation (**Jacob et al., 1995b; Gohet et al., 1996**), , according to **Eschbach et al. (1984)**, has the effect of activating the metabolism of the laticifers and also results in increasing the inorganic phosphorus content (**Jacob et al., 1988**). This energy can be further enhanced by the fact that stimulated treatments, including coated ones that have had a stimulating effect on rubber production, have enough sugar resources, which is the raw material of the rubber bio-synthesis (**Jacob et al., 1988 and 1995a**).

The presence of thiol compounds is essential in all the cells because these molecules are able to neutralize the molecules of active forms of oxygen (FAO: O^{2-} , OH^- and H_2O_2) which are classic by-products of any cellular metabolism (**Fridovich , 1978**). Such a production of toxic oxygen remains weak but real when the metabolism is normal. However, it can reach a considerable level when the cell is under stress, whatever be its origin (**Elstner, 1982**). By trapping toxic forms of oxygen, thiols protect the cell compartmentalization of latex and, consequently, the functioning of laticifers (**Jacob et al., 1987**). This protects against the appearance and advancement of the tapping panel dryness. However, in this study, coated treatment alone is distinguished by its highest tapping panel dryness rate, although the thiol content is moderate, compared to the reference values established by **Jacob et al (1987)**. This result would not be related to the metabolic activity of the tree, but to the inhibitory effect of the acetate that is a component of the vinyl paint used as a protective coating.

CONCLUSION

The use of vinyl paint alone as protective coating of the tapping panel of rubber trees has unacceptable characteristics. The use of the protective coating alone is unfavorable for the iso-diametric growth of the trunk and the thickening of the bark of the trees. In addition, the protection of the tapping panel by the coating alone causes more tapping panel dryness in the treated trees. These listed depressive aspects can be overcome by the addition of ANA methyl ester to the water-based vinyl paint coating. Thus, the water-based vinyl paint can be used as rubber panel protectant coating only if it is combined with 5% concentrated ANA methyl ester.

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